

Kinetics and Mechanism of Electro-reduction of Nickel(II) Complexes: Polarographic Studies

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The polarographic behaviour of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3^{2+}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ -EDTA complex and $\text{Ni}(\text{bigH})_2^{2+}$ in 0.1M aqueous KNO_3 medium has been studied. Each species has been found to undergo a diffusion controlled two-electron reduction at the DME; the process is irreversible for all the complexes except $\text{Ni}(\text{bigH})_2^{2+}$ which undergoes reversible reduction. For the irreversible systems (except $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ where there are other complications) the values of the rate constant, k_r , of the electrode process at a reference potential of -1.0 V vs. SCE have been evaluated from polarographic characteristics following known methods. From the k_r values of each system at four different temperatures in the range of 25° to 40° the corresponding activation energy, E_a , has also been evaluated. Results indicate that for complexes of charge type $2+$ the ease of reduction increases in the sequence of decreasing Dq value of the complex, while for complexes of the same Dq value the ease of reduction follows the sequence cationic > non-ionic > anionic. A plausible mechanism of electron transfer has been discussed.

THE rates of irreversible and diffusion controlled electroreduction of bis(ethylenediamine)copper(II) ion and bis(glycinato)copper(II) at the dropping mercury electrode have been studied earlier¹ making use of the relation as given in equation (1) based on Koutecky's derivation² and the Oldham and Parry's graphical method³ of evaluating E_1 and α values using the relation given in equation (2):

$$E_1 = E_r + 2.303 RT / \alpha n F \log \{0.89 k_r \sqrt{t/D}\} \dots (1)$$

$$-E = -E_1 + 2.303 RT / \alpha n F \log \{X(5.5 - X) / 5(1 - X)\} \dots (2)$$

where k_r is the rate constant for the electro-reduction process at a reference potential E_r (of the DME), t is the drop time at the potential E_r , D is the diffusion coefficient of the electroactive species undergoing the reduction, α is the transfer coefficient, $X = i_E / i_{lim}$ and all other terms have their usual significance. Equation (2) is valid in the entire range where $0 \leq X \leq 1$.

Similar studies on several complexes of nickel(II) are reported in this communication.

Experimental

Materials and reagents:

Tris(ethylenediamine)nickel(II)nitrate, $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2$.—This was prepared by cooling a warm concentrated aqueous solution containing nickel(II) nitrate and ethylenediamine in slight excess of 1:3 molar ratio when the complex separated out. This was recrystallized from water (containing a little ethylenediamine) and dried over calcium chloride in *vacuo*.

*Bis(glycinato)nickel(II) dihydrate*⁴, $\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, *bis(acetylacetonato)nickel(II) dihydrate*⁵, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and *bis(biguanide)nickel(II) Chloride dihydrate*⁶, $\text{Ni}(\text{bigH})_2 \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were prepared by methods described in literature. Purity of all the complexes prepared were checked by analysis:

Complex	Found(%)		Calcd.(%)	
	Ni	N	Ni	N
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_2)_3(\text{NO}_3)_2$	16.1	30.6	16.19	30.88
$\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{NCH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	24.0	11.4	24.19	11.54
$\text{Ni}(\text{H}_3\text{CCOCHCOCH}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	19.9	—	20.05	—
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5)_2 \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	16.0	38.2	15.97	38.07

Nickel(II)-ammine and nickel(II)-EDTA complexes were formed *in situ*. An aqueous solution (0.001M) of nickel(II) nitrate containing 1M ammonia was used for the former⁷ and a similar solution containing 0.001M disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid ($\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{Y}$) in place of the ammonia and adjusted to pH ca. 3.4 by adding NaOH was used for the latter⁸; these are known to contain $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{YH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ respectively as the most predominant complex species in solution. Triton X-100 (Rohm & Haas Co., USA) was used as a suppressor of polarographic maxima; a 1% stock solution was prepared in double distilled water. All other chemicals used were of reagent quality (G.R., E. Merck or A.R., BDH) or else purified before use by usual methods. Distilled water redistilled in an all-glass still with a little KMnO_4 and KOH was used for preparing all the solutions; stock solutions were stored in Jena glass bottles.

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Hydrogen gas prepared by electrolysis was made oxygen free by passing over a bed of pure copper turnings kept at ca. 450° and this was used for deaerating the solutions before recording the polarograms.

Apparatus and procedure :

A manual polarograph (CLO-2A, Toshniwal, India) with a sensitive galvanometer (Polyflex, sensitivity 0.362 μ A per mm of scale division, Toshniwal make) was used to record the polarograms using a cell with a dropping mercury electrode (DME) and an external saturated calomel electrode (SCE) which was connected to the cell through Agar-KCl+Agar-KNO₃ salt bridges connected in series; resistance of the SCE with all the salt bridges was about 420 ohms which was small enough ensuring negligible i_R drop at this part of the electrical circuit. The cell temperature was maintained constant by means of a water thermostat in which both the polarographic cell and the SCE were kept immersed. All potentials were measured against the SCE as reference. The galvanometer was calibrated before use to convert the deflection (mm) into current (μ A). At a mercury height (h_{Hg}) of 30 cm the capillary of the DME had the following characteristics (in open circuit in 0.1M KNO₃ solution containing 0.002% Triton X-100) : $m = 2.56$ mg sec⁻¹, $t = 3.12$ sec. The compositions of the solutions studied were complex = 0.001M; KNO₃ (or KCl in the case of the biguanide complex only)^(a) = 0.1M; Triton X-100 = 0.002%.

A Philips conductivity bridge (PR 9500/90) was used for conductance measurements. From the ionic conductance values the diffusion coefficients, D , were evaluated using the following Nernst relation^b :

$$D = \frac{RT}{ZF^2} \lambda_0 \quad \dots (3)$$

where Z is the charge on the ion and λ_0 is the equivalent conductance of the ion at infinite dilution and the other terms have their usual significance. For pH measurements a Philips pH meter (PR 9405 M/90) was used.

Of all the species studied this method of evaluating the diffusion coefficient from conductance value making use of equation (3) was naturally applicable only to the ionic species such as Ni(en)₃²⁺, Ni(bigH)₂²⁺ and Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺. It was reasonably assumed that the diffusion coefficient of Ni(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂²⁺ is nearly identical to that of Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺ while that of Ni(YH)(H₂O)⁻ nearly identical to that of Ni(en)₃²⁺; such approximations being acceptable for D values needed in evaluating n values (number of electrons involved in the electrode process) from the Ilkovic equation, since n value is always a whole number and hence from the approximate n value calculated using the approximate D value the actual n value can be easily obtained (being the whole number

nearest to the approximate n value). Similarly, for Ni(gly)₂ and Ni(acac)₂ the diffusion coefficients were assumed to be nearly the same as that of Ni(bigH)₂²⁺.

In order to find the value of the ionic conductance of Ni(en)₃²⁺ ion under the experimental conditions, the conductance of a solution containing 0.001M Ni(en)₃(NO₃)₂ and 0.1M ethylenediamine (to completely suppress the dissociation of Ni(en)₃²⁺ into the bis species) was measured from which the measured value of the conductance of an aqueous solution of 0.1M ethylenediamine under identical conditions was subtracted to arrive at the conductance of the solution due to Ni(en)₃(NO₃)₂ only at 0.001M concentration. From this value the equivalent conductance of Ni(en)₃²⁺ ion was calculated as usual by subtracting from the equivalent conductance of the complex salt (229.5 at 30°) the known value of the ionic conductance (77.75 at 30°) of the nitrate ion. This was an approximate value since the equivalent conductance of the nitrate ion which was used from literature data is for infinite dilution, while the experimentally determined values are at a concentration of 0.001M. Similar approximate values for the diffusion coefficients of Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺ and Ni(bigH)₂²⁺ were obtained from the measured conductances of aqueous solutions (0.001M) of Ni(H₂O)₆(NO₃)₂ (nickel(II) nitrate solution) and Ni(bigH)₂Cl₂, respectively. Using these approximate D values the n values were found to be nearly 2 (2 ± 0.2) in all the cases studied indicating that n is actually 2. Using this value of $n = 2$ accurate values of D were then evaluated at different experimental temperatures and for the different complexes using the Ilkovic equation and the experimentally measured values of i_a , m and t . The accurate D values thus obtained were used in evaluating the rate constants, k_r , using equation (1), at different temperatures and for different complexes at a reference potential of -1.0 volt vs. SCE.

However, in order to apply the Ilkovic equation it was first necessary to establish that the waves were diffusion controlled. This was shown to be true in each of the cases studied from the constancy (within the limits of experimental error) of the $i_a/(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ value (where $h_{eff} \approx h_{Hg} - 3.1/m^{1/3}t^{1/3}$) for i_a values at 30, 40 and 50 cm.

Equation (1) applies only for an irreversible (but diffusion controlled) wave and in all the cases studied, except in the case of Ni(bigH)₂²⁺, the irreversible nature of the wave was established from the slope of the usual 'log plot' of $\log\{i/(i_a - i)\}$ vs. $-E$ being much higher than that expected ($2.303RT/nF$) for a reversible wave. Only in the case of Ni(bigH)₂²⁺ the slope of the log plot was that expected for a reversible wave. Hence, in this case, as well as in the case of Ni(acac)₂ where there are other complications (see 'Results and Discussion') evaluation of k_r was not possible. In all the other cases k_r was evaluated at a reference potential of -1.0 volt vs. SCE at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40° under otherwise identical conditions and from these values the activation energy, E_a , was evaluated graphically in each case as usual making use of the Arrhenius equation.

^(a) Since Ni(bigH)₂²⁺ gets precipitated in 0.1M KNO₃ as the sparingly soluble nitrate, in this case 0.1M KCl was used; in all the other cases 0.1M KNO₃ was used.

Results and Discussion

Tris(ethylenediamine)nickel(II) ion.—The polarogram of Ni(en)_3^{2+} (0.001M) in 0.1M aqueous KNO_3 having 0.002% Triton X-100 showed two waves which were not at all well separated and hence accurate evaluation of i_a values of each of the two waves was not possible. But even with the approximate values the ratio of the wave heights i_{a_2}/i_{a_1} was found to be fairly constant (ca. 0.7 at 30°) and independent of h_{Hg} . In presence of excess ethylenediamine (0.1M) a single wave appeared which began at the same potential as that of the second wave observed in the absence of added ethylenediamine. Hence, the two waves observed in the absence of added ethylenediamine were due to the *tris* and the *bis* complexes in equilibrium in the solution:

and the single wave in the presence of excess ethylenediamine was due to Ni(en)_3^{2+} . This wave ($n = 2$) was found to be diffusion controlled and irreversible for which k_r and E_a values were evaluated as outlined earlier (see 'Procedure').

Bis(glycinato)nickel(II).—The polarogram of Ni(gly)_2 (0.001M) in 0.1M KNO_3 having 0.002% Triton X-100 also showed two waves which merged into a single wave due to the *bis* species in presence of 0.01M glycine with 0.003M NaOH. This wave is also diffusion controlled and irreversible for which k_r and E_a values were also evaluated.

Bis(acetylacetonato)nickel(II).—A 0.001M solution of Ni(acac)_2 in 0.1M KNO_3 containing Triton X-100 (0.002%) gave two well separated waves (E_1 values -0.966 V and -1.465 V vs. SCE respectively) for which the ratio of i_a values (i_{a_1}/i_{a_2}) was found to be constant (0.54 at 30°) irrespective of h_{Hg} . Addition of excess free acetylacetonone did not produce any effect, while excess of acetylacetonone in presence of NaOH caused a considerable lowering of the total wave height. Therefore, the complex was studied in the absence of any added acetylacetonone and alkali. It was observed that with increasing dilution or with increasing temperature, the ratio i_{a_1}/i_{a_2} increased. This is compatible with the fact that with increasing dilution or increasing temperature the extent of dissociation of the Ni(acac)_2 in solution increases. Hence the first wave at less negative potential was due to the mono complex while the second one at more negative potential was due to the *bis* complex present in equilibrium:

That the reductions of both the species were diffusion controlled were shown from the constancy of the $i_a/(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ values, at four different heights of the mercury column, for each of the waves. Naturally total current was also diffusion controlled. As it was not possible to calculate exactly the relative amounts of the two species, determination of n value for each individual step was not possible, but attempt

was made to calculate n for the total wave height considering the diffusion coefficient value of Ni(bigH)_2^{2+} as representing the diffusion coefficient of the species present in solution. The n value thus obtained was 2.1 suggesting that two electrons were involved in the reduction process. Usual 'log plot' of each of the waves was a good straight line but with much higher slopes than expected for a reversible reduction. However, because of complications due to the presence of two different species in solution, the relative proportions of which were not known and which also changed with temperature, evaluation of k_r was not possible.

Ni(II)-EDTA complex.—In 0.1M KNO_3 in presence of Triton X-100 (0.002%) the solution which contained $\text{Ni(YH)(H}_2\text{O)}^-$ (see 'Experimental') gave a single wave which was diffusion controlled and irreversible and for this k_r and E_a values were evaluated as usual.

Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺ ion.—For this a solution of nickel(II) nitrate (0.001M) in 0.1M KNO_3 (in presence of 0.002% Triton X-100) was studied. Reduction ($n = 2$) occurred in a single step which was diffusion controlled and irreversible and for this k_r and E_a values were evaluated as usual.

Ni(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂²⁺ ion.—In 0.1M KNO_3 in presence of Triton X-100 (0.002%) the solution which contained $\text{Ni(NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}$ (see 'Experimental') gave a single wave ($n = 2$) which was diffusion controlled and irreversible and for this k_r and E_a values were evaluated as usual.

Ni(bigH)₂²⁺ ion.—The polarogram of 0.001M $\text{Ni(bigH)}_2\text{Cl}_2$ in 0.1M KCl (in presence of 0.002% Triton X-100) showed a very small pre-wave beginning at a potential of ca. -1.25 V vs. SCE and attaining the limiting value at ca. -1.35 V vs. SCE; this was followed by the main wave beginning at ca. -1.52 V vs. SCE ($E_1 = -1.575$ V vs. SCE). The pre-wave being very small (its height was only ca. 6% of the height of the main wave) was neglected. May be, as in the case of some of the other nickel(II) complexes mentioned earlier this pre-wave was due to the presence in solution of a trace amount of the *mono* complex present in equilibrium with the *bis* species. The main wave ($n = 2$) was found to be diffusion controlled, but unlike in the other cases mentioned above, it was found to be reversible (observed slope of the 'log plot' at 30° was 0.029). Hence, in this case k_r could not be evaluated as in the other cases which gave irreversible waves.

The rate constants (at 25°) for the electro-reduction of the different nickel(II) complexes studied, which gave only one irreversible diffusion controlled wave, and their other characteristics are given in Table 1 for comparison.

From a comparison of the k_r and E_1 values it is seen that for Ni(II) complexes of different charge type (viz., 2+, 0 and 1-) having the same $\bar{v}$ value, the ease of reduction decreases in the sequence $\text{Ni(NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+} > \text{Ni(gly)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 > \text{Ni(YH)(H}_2\text{O)}^-$. Again, in the case of the cationic complexes having a charge of 2+, the ease of reduction decreases in

TABLE 1.—CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES FOR ELECTRO-REDUCTION OF SOME NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES (Ni^{II} + 2e → Ni⁰) AT THE DME(Polarographic data at 25° in 0.1M KNO₃ in presence of 0.002% Triton X-100; Complex, 0.001M)

Complex	$\bar{\nu}$, kK ^(a)	$-E_{1/2}$, V vs SCE	10 ³ D, ^(b) cm ² sec ⁻¹	α	k_r , cm.sec ⁻¹ (at -1.0V vs. SCE)	E_a , kcal.-mole ⁻¹ (at -1.0 V vs. SCE)
Ni(H ₂ O) ₆ ²⁺	8.5	0.997	8.804	0.411	1.89 × 10 ⁻³	19.9
Ni(NH ₃) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂ ²⁺	10.0 ^(c)	1.030	10.690	0.721	3.51 × 10 ⁻⁴	20.7
Ni(en) ₃ ²⁺	11.2	1.345	7.488	0.257	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁶	26.9
Ni(gly) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ ^(d)	10.0	1.163	3.839	0.537	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁶	14.6
Ni(YH)(H ₂ O) ⁻	10.0	1.535	7.460	0.300	6.13 × 10 ⁻⁹	15.2

(a) Wave-number values of the principal absorption band of nickel(II) complexes have been taken from literature¹⁰.

(b) Calculated using the Ilkovic equation (see 'Procedure').

(c) Calculated value based on the concept of 'average environment'.¹¹(d) The bisglycinato species possibly exists in aqueous solution as a six-coordinated diaquo complex.¹²

the sequence Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺ > Ni(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂²⁺ > Ni(en)₃²⁺ with increase in $\bar{\nu}$ value.

For a six-coordinated complex of Ni(II), $\bar{\nu}$ is related to its Dq(average) value and hence the results indicate that with increasing ligand field splitting electron transfer from the electrode to the Ni(II) in a complex becomes increasingly difficult. In a six-coordinate complex of Ni(II) the eight *d* electrons are accommodated in the different orbitals as follows :

At the electrode surface if the Ni(II) complex is oriented with its *xy*-plane perpendicular to the electrode surface then the $\sigma_{x^2-y^2}^*$ orbital would be destabilized by the electrostatic field of the electrode and would thus be higher in energy than the $\sigma_{z^2}^*$ orbital even in the case of a six-coordinated complex having six identical ligands which has an undistorted octahedral structure in the ground state; same also holds good for *d*_{xy} orbital which would be higher in energy than the *d*_{xz}, *d*_{yz} pair. The $\sigma_{x^2-y^2}^*$ orbital is suitably oriented to accept electrons from the electrode surface to cause the reduction. But for this process to occur $\sigma_{x^2-y^2}^*$ orbital has to be vacated by transferring the electron to be paired in the relatively lower energy $\sigma_{z^2}^*$ orbital. The net energy required for the process would naturally contribute to the activation energy thus accounting for a relatively slow electron transfer which gives rise to an irreversible wave. In the sequence Ni(H₂O)₆²⁺ to Ni(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂²⁺ to Ni(en)₃²⁺ the Dq(average) value increases as also the sigma donation from the ligands. But with increasing sigma donation the electron affinity of the central Ni(II) decreases making the electron transfer less favourable (i.e., decrease in the ease of reduction) in the same sequence (increasing Dq) of the complexes as has been observed.

Bis(biguanide) nickel(II) ion is diamagnetic in the solid salts and is thus a complex of a strong field ligand which therefore retains its square-planar geometry even in aqueous solution¹². In such a case the eight *d* electrons of Ni(II) are distributed as (*d*_{xz})²(*d*_{yz})²(*d*_{x²-y²})²(*d*_{xy})² with the $\sigma_{x^2-y^2}^*$ orbital lying vacant and thus capable of accepting electrons from the electrode surface leading to fast electron transfer to give rise to a reversible wave as has actually been observed.

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